

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NAKOOJO****FIRST NAME: FRANCIS****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 7%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE PHGH ACA-401D

1. What are the two common Turabian or Chicago systems of source citation widely used in humanitarian and social sciences?

- Author and Date.
- Notes and Bibliography.
- Notes-Date and Author-Bibliography.
- Notes-Bibliography and Author-Date.¹**

2. Choose the correct statement(s) regarding capitalization and use of italics in the Author-Date style.

- All titles must be capitalized using the headline style.

1. Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth Edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 141.

- Italicize titles of larger and smaller entities but use quotation marks and roman type for titles of work not yet published.
 - Italicize titles of larger entities and use roman type and quotation marks for titles of smaller entities and work not formally published.²**
 - Headline style is used for titles in languages other than English, while sentence style applies to titles in English.
3. Which statement(s) best describes the order of elements in Notes-Bibliography style?
- The elements in notes and bibliography entries follow the same general order (author, title, and publication facts) for all sources.
 - Notes entries present authors' first name first, while bibliography entries present authors' last names first.
 - Notes entries citing specific passages usually include page numbers, while bibliography entries do not.
 - All the above are correct statements.³**
4. In quantitative research, the term validity refers to:
- The extent to which a measure is consistent and stable in measuring what it intended to measure.

2. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations*, 234.

3. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations*, 154.

- The extent to which an instrument or test measures what it intended to measure.⁴**
- The extent to which an instrument or test demonstrates adequate internal consistency.
- How meaningful it is to generalize based on the research.
5. Which of the following statements best describes construct validity?
- Construct validity is concerned with evidence that the content of the measure is congruent with the conceptual or theoretical basis of the instrument or test.
- Construct validity is concerned with evidence supporting a hypothesized relationship between the content of the measure and other measures of the construct.
- Construct validity is concerned with the individual perception that an instrument, test, questionnaire, or observation appears to measure what they are told it is intended to measure.
- Construct validity is concerned with the congruence between what an instrument or test actually measures and what it is designed to measure.⁵**
6. Plagiarism can be defined as
- Representing another person's works, words, or ideas as your own.

4. James P. Sampson, Jr., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Florida: Educational Psychology and Learning Systems College Publications, 2017), 40.

5. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 41.

- Paraphrasing another's ideas without attribution to the author.
- Summarizing an article and putting information in one's own words but not citing the source.
- All above⁶**

7. Select the correct statement(s) regarding research hypothesis.

- A research hypothesis is applicable in quantitative and qualitative research.
- A hypothesis can be stated in null form, directional form, or both.
- A null hypothesis assumes that there are no differences among variables. Any significant difference found among participant groups can be in either direction.⁷**
- A null hypothesis assumes that any significant difference between variables and participant groups is in a specific direction and that a significant relationship among variables will be positively or negatively correlated.

8. Regarding summarizing and paraphrasing work sources;

- There is no difference between summarizing a source and paraphrasing a source.
- Paraphrased sources require citations, while summarized sources do not.
- Paraphrase when you need only the point of a passage, summarize when the specific words of a passage are less important than the meaning.

6. Laurent Gleenerwerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2024), 34.

7. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 35.

Summarize when you need only the point of a passage, paraphrase when the particular words of a passage are less important than the meaning,⁸

9. Which of the following is not the primary use of a colon (:) in WHO style punctuation?

- To demarcate the contrast between two statements more sharply than a semicolon.
- To separate main clauses with different subjects not connected by a conjunction.⁹**
- To indicate that a second statement explains or amplifies the first.
- To introduce a list or series (never followed by a dash).

10. Which statement is incorrect regarding the WHO numerical system of citation and referencing?

- The numerical system maintains a flow of the text and is less distracting.
- A reader familiar with the literature in the field can recognize the work from in-text citations without turning to the reference list.¹⁰**
- It is space-efficient and easy to compile and look up references.
- Revision requires the renumbering of the citations in the text and the references.

8. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations*, 50.

9. World Health Organization, *Who Style-Guide*, Second Edition (Geneva: WHO Publications, 2013), 32.

10. World Health Organization, *Who Style-Guide*, 37.

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Gleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2024.

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World Health Organization. *Who Style-Guide*. Second Edition. Geneva: WHO Publications, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.